

SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE - THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS

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The purpose of the work: from the most used forms of Medicine in medical practice – the widespread distribution of the naming and application of tablets and solutions in medical practice among students, the formation of the correct application skills in prescriptions and the assistance of students in our country, even if they are little less likely to apply the names of drug forms in international nomenclature.

Information and methods of work: Tablets (tabulettae): tablets are a form of solid medicine that is dosed to apply inside and out.

The tablets are flat, circular, double-topped, ovoid or in the form of another plate. If they contain toxic substances, the tablets are colored coiled – red, others are colored blue.

If the substance of the drug is in very small quantities, more filler substances are added in the tablet: Sugar, Glucose, Sodium bicarbonate, Calcium phosphate, etc.

Tablets are divided into types of pressed tablets (tabulettae compressae), shaped tablets (tabulettae friabiles), and coated tablets (tabulettae obductae).

In tablets, sugar, milk sugar, dextrin, starch, etc. act as a coating.

The tablets are divided into oral (oriblettae seu tabulettae perorales), sublingual (resoriblettae seu tabulettae sublinguales); for injection solutions (injectabilettae seu tabulettae pro injectionibus); for chewing solution-making (solublettae seu tabulettae pro gargarismatis) types.

When tablets that do not have a conditional designation are written in recipes, the name of the drug substance is indicated, the dosage is determined, the amount and form are written in the Subscriptio part. For example:

Rp.: Extracti Belladonnae 0.013

Natrii hydrocarbonatis 0.25

Da tales doses numĕro 6 in tabulettis

Signa: 1 tablet 3 times a day.

Tablets that are standard can be written in recipes even when their dosage is not prescribed. In such cases, the name of the form of the drug in the prescription should stand in Accusativus Pluralis (plural number of Income agreement). For example:

Rp.: Tabulettas "Cornella" obductas N 50

Da. Signa: 1 tablet 3 times a day.

As such, tablets of one composition, the dosage of which is indicated, are written in the recipe according to the above rule. For example:

Rp.: Tabulettas Platyphyllĭni hydrotartrĀtis 0,005 numĕro 6

Da. Signa: 1 tablet 2 – 3 times a day.

Solutiōnes (Solutiōnes) is a homogeneous transparent liquid made by completely dissolving (solid, liquid or gaseous) medicinal substances in solvents.

Solvents destired water (aqua destillĀta), ethyl alcohol (Spirĭtus aethylĭcus 95%, 90%, 70%), it can be glycerin (Glycerinum,i,n), Vaseline (Vaselinum,i,n), olive oil (oleum Olivarum), peach oil (oleum Persicorum), almond oil (oleum AmygdalĀrum), sunflower oil (oleum Helianthi).

Depending on the type of solvents, solutions are divided into:

- aqueous solutions (solutiōnes aquōsae);
- alcohol solutions (solutiōnes spirituōsae);
- oil solutions (solutiōnes oleōsae seu olea medicĀta);
- glycerol solutions (solutiōnes glycerinĀtae).

Solutions according to reception are divided into:

1. Solutions for injection (Solutiōnes pro injectionĭbus);
2. Solutions for external application (Solutiōnes ad usum externum).

They can be divided into (gargarismĀta) for rinsing the throat (gargarismĀta), lotions (lotiōnes), for rinsing the oral cavity (collutōria), clysmā, for enema (cnemĀta seu clysmĀta), for lubrication (litūrae), for sprinkling, for spraying (perlotiōnes), for rubbing (frictiōnes), etc.

3. Solutions for application to internal (Solutiōnes ad usum internim seu solutiōnes pro anaesthesiĀ).

Solutions are found in ampoules (in ampullis), spritz-Tubas (in spritz-tubūlis), rectum pipettes, 3-5 ml. from microlysmus to (inrectiolis) solutions are produced in form. Solutions are written in methods that are abbreviated and extended in recipes. When writing solutions in recipes in a reduced way, Recĭpe (Rp.after the word:), the drug form –Solutions is written and the name of the

drug substance, the level of the solution in percentages and the amount of the drug are written. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Menthōli oleōsae 1% 10 ml

Da. Signa: 2-3 drops 3 times a day.

In recipes written in an extended manner, the solutions are called Recīpe (Rp. after the word:), the name of the drug substance, its amount and solvent are written. For example:

Rp.: Mehthōli 0.1

Phenylii salicylātis 0.3

Olei Vaselīni 9.6 ml

Misce. Da. Signa: 2-3 drops to the nose 2 times a day.

Injection solutions (Solutiōnes pro injectionībus) are produced in ampoules for subcutaneous injection, for muscle injection, for intravenous injection, and for other solution purposes.

About the sterility of the injection is written in the Subscription part of the recipe. The words in ampullis (in ampoules), pro injectionībus (for injection) are written there. Sterileīsa when solutions that are not in the ampoule are written in recipes! (Boil and clean!), Sterilisētur (boil and clean!) is written. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Magnesii sulfātis 25% - 10 ml

Da tales doses numēro 5 in ampullis.

Signa: be sent 10 ml. between the muscles every day.

Rp.: Solutiōnis Acetylcysteīni pro injectionībus 10% 2 ml numēro 10

Da in ampullis. Signa: be sent 2 ml. between muscles from 3 times a day.

In the Subscription part of the recipe, when the pharmacy-made injection solutions are written in the prescriptions, "Sterilisētur!" (Boil clean!) or "Sterilīsa!" (Clean it up!) is written as. In such cases, the name and amount of the drug substance and solvents will be written. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Natrii iodīdi 10% - 200 ml

Sterilisētur!

Da in vitro nigro.

Signa: be sent 10 ml. between the muscles.

Solutions for injections in ampoules are written indicating the dose amount. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Morphīni 1% 1 ml

Dentur tales doses numēro 6 in ampullis.

Signētur: from 1 ml. subcutaneous.

In recipes, the type of solvent of course is indicated when alcohol or oil solutions are written. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Camphōrae oleōsae 20% - 2 ml

Da tales doses numēro 6 in ampullis.

Signa: be sent 2 ml. between the muscles.

Solutions for external application (Solutiōnes ad usum externum) are written in recipes in a shortened and extended way. Recipes indicate the form of the drug, the name of the drug substance, the type of solution (alcohol or oil), the level in percent and the total amount when written in a reduced way. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Acīdi salicylīci spirituōsae 1% 10 ml

Da. Signa: to apply to the skin.

When aqueous solutions are written in a reduced method in recipes, the solvent is not indicated. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Kalii permanganātis 0.1% 500 ml

Da. Signa: to wash wounds.

All components of the drug, as well as solvents, are fully indicated when solutions for external application are written in the extended method in recipes. For example:

Rp.: Alumīnis 4,0

Acīdi borīci 6,0

Aquae destillātae 200 ml

Misce. Da.

Signa: to rub.

Rp.: Natrii tetraborātis 2.5

Glycerīni 50 ml

Spirītus aethylīci 0.5% ad 10 ml

Misce. Da.

Signa: to apply to the skin.

Tablets can also be used to prepare solutions for external application. For example:

Rp.: Furacillīni ad usum externum 0,02 numēro 10

Da. Signa: dissolve 1 tablet in 100 ml of water. To shake.

Solutions for application to internal (Solutiōnes ad usum internum) are not indicated by solvent – distilled water (aqua destillāta), purified water (aqua purificāta) when written in the abbreviated method in recipes.

Rp.: Solutiōnis Calcii chlorīdi 5% 200 ml

Da. Signa: 1 table spoon 3-4 times a day after meals.

All components of the drug, as well as solvents, are fully indicated when the solutions for application to the internal are written in the extended method in the recipes. For example:

Rp.: Cupri sulfātis 0.5

Aquae destillātae 50 ml

Misce. Da.

Signa: 1 table spoon when thirsty.

Solutions are also prepared for anesthesia (loss of sensation). Solutions for anesthesia are called Solutiōnes ad anaesthesiam. For example:

Rp.: Solutiōnis Novocaīni 0.25-200 ml

Da. Signa. For anesthesia.

Rp.: Novocaīni 1.25

Natrii chlōridi 3.0

Kalii chlōridi 0.038

Calcii chlōridi 0.062

Aquae pro injectionībus 500 ml

Misceātur. Sterilisētur!

Detur. Signētur: for anesthesia.

Conclusion: we have shown differences in the name of tablets and solutions and examples from recipes. Many of our students do not distinguish between designations once they have little education. The result may be incorrect conclusions from articles or theses written in foreign languages, or incomplete translation. Our goal is to help students diligently learn new medical terms in learning and effectively apply them in future practice.

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